

⟨H/RADIOSA⟩: Recommended Approaches for the Development of Interoperable Open Semantic Artefacts in the Heritage Domain

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Abstract

This paper offers actionable recommendations and best practices for developing semantic artefacts in the Heritage field. Aimed at both experts and non-specialists, it highlights the importance of adopting FAIR and Linked Data principles. Drawing on a survey of existing tools and a review of relevant literature, the ⟨H/RADIOSA⟩ initiative proposes guidelines to bridge the gap between domain-specific needs and technical standards. These recommendations serve as a call to action for researchers and practitioners to foster the creation of high-quality, interoperable semantic artefacts.

CCS Concepts

• **Computing methodologies** → **Ontology engineering**; • **Information systems** → **Ontologies**; **Thesauri**; **Dictionaries**; • **Software and its engineering** → **Version control**; **Documentation**;

1. Introduction

The *Heritage: Recommended Approaches for the Development of Interoperable Open Semantic Artefacts* (⟨H/RADIOSA⟩) initiative aims to establish a set of guidelines and best practices for developing semantic artefacts in the Heritage field. The idea for ⟨H/RADIOSA⟩ emerged during the development of an ontology tailored to the Heritage Science domain within the framework of the H2IOSC project (<https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/>) [SVR25], intended for use within the Italian E-RIHS infrastructure (<https://www.e-rihs.it/>). A preliminary survey conducted to assess the status of pre-existing tools in this domain revealed uneven standards and frequent failures to comply with some of the basic tenets of the Semantic Web [SV24k, SV24h].

This paper offers initial, actionable guidelines for developing semantic artefacts in the Heritage field, targeting both practitioners and end-users. It also supports subject-matter experts unfamiliar with semantic tools in understanding their implications. The goal is to bridge the gap between effective domain modeling and the minimal requirements for producing FAIR- and Linked Data-compliant artefacts. The ⟨H/RADIOSA⟩ recommendations are framed as actions to encourage progress in standardizing semantic artefact development within the Heritage community.

This initiative is largely inspired by the work of the OBO Foundry, a community of experts in biomedicine dedicated to harmonizing domain ontologies and promoting best practices among its members [JMO*21]. While the OBO Foundry primarily focuses on ontologies, ⟨H/RADIOSA⟩ has a broader scope, addressing semantic artefacts in general. Additionally, ⟨H/RADIOSA⟩ aims to incorporate W3C best practices more rigorously.

The term ontology, in its computational sense, is often used with a broad meaning in discussions surrounding semantic technologies. At times, it refers to the formalization of a domain of knowledge, encompassing thesauri and other Knowledge Organization Systems (KOS). In other instances, it denotes a specific type of KOS—namely, those that incorporate logical relationships between terms to describe a domain of knowledge. To address this ambiguity, the authors consistently adopt the term semantic artefact in this work. A semantic artefact is defined as "a machine-actionable and -readable formalisation of a conceptualisation enabling sharing and reuse by humans and machines" [HLFC*20, 12], and has recently been described at length in the frameworks of the FAIRsFAIR and FAIR-IMPACT projects (see below). Semantic artefacts (SAs) thus include ontologies, thesauri, metadata standards, and all resources situated at the intersection of these categories. For clarity, the term *Heritage Semantic Artefact* (HSA) is used here to specifically refer to semantic artefacts developed or particularly relevant for the Heritage domain.

2. Actions

The *Heritage — Semantic Resources and Interoperability Survey* (H-SeTIS) [SV24h, SV24k] revealed significant inconsistencies in the development of HSAs. This issue is not unique to the Heritage domain; however, given the urgent demand for effective and sustainable data management and research tools in this field, the authors argue that it stands to benefit significantly from such an initiative.

While there is a substantial body of literature on best practices

for ontology development and SAs more broadly, the H-SeTIS survey revealed significant inconsistencies in how these practices are applied within the Heritage domain. In response, *H/RADIOSA* does not aim to reinvent the wheel, but rather to offer a practical toolkit that organizes and highlights often-overlooked practices. It also provides guidance on relevant resources that elucidate their implementation. In addition, it must be stressed that the scientific panorama of SAs development is quickly and constantly evolving. This is due both to a recent semantic trend, and to initiatives aiming at putting into practice the long-awaited implementations of FAIRness in the production and management of research data and resources.

This paper highlights four key sets of guidelines identified through H-SeTIS as requiring particular attention, for which best practices and relevant literature are proposed. Emphasis is placed on aligning with recent standards such as Linked Data and FAIR principles. Although machine-readable and -actionable SAs have existed for over two decades, the advent of these paradigms—Linked (Open) Data (theoretically introduced in 2006) and FAIR guidelines (first published in 2016)—has significantly reshaped practices. Adoption, particularly in the heritage field, remains a work in progress, with FAIR data management now central to various initiatives, especially within EU-funded research.

2.1. Be FAIR

The FAIR data guidelines—defining the principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability—were first established in 2014, and were formally published in 2016 [WDA*16]. These principles were designed to improve data management and stewardship, enhancing the discoverability, accessibility, and reuse of scientific data across disciplines. Recognizing their importance, the European Commission endorsed the FAIR principles as part of its open access policies for scientific research data beginning in 2018 [Com18]. Since then, the Commission has actively promoted their implementation through the establishment of dedicated task forces, including the EU Commission Expert Group on FAIR Data [Eur18], and the FAIR in Practice Task Force of the EOSC FAIR Working Group [Eur20]. These initiatives reflect a broader European commitment to making research data more open, transparent, and reusable by design.

The authors of the FAIR guidelines identified the primary obstacle to efficient data collection for research not in the lack of advanced technologies, but in the poor management and stewardship of digital assets. Inadequately organized and maintained data resources limit their integration and usability within the broader scientific ecosystem. The ultimate goal of implementing the FAIR principles is to ensure that digital objects, such as datasets, are seamlessly integrated into the scientific publication lifecycle, just like traditional research outputs. This integration aims to establish research data as a fundamental component of scholarly communication, fostering innovation and collaboration within the scientific community. In its original formulation, FAIRness is a characteristic primarily pertaining to data, their production, and management. In recent years, the basic tenets of FAIRness have been extended to the development of SAs [GP20, PEGC20, CGMM21, LFBK*22, XJG*23]. Specifically, the use of FAIR SAs enhances

interoperability and promotes reuse, particularly when SAs are encoded using a shared standard language. The extension of FAIRness to SA development is among the topics investigated in the EU funded FAIR-IMPACT project (<https://doi.org/10.3030/101057344>, 2022–2025), which aims at integrating FAIR solutions in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

As highlighted in the FAIR-IMPACT project deliverable on defining assessment methods for the FAIRness of SAs [GPF*23], one of the most significant challenges in implementing FAIR solutions for these particular digital objects is that many of them were developed using methodologies that predate the FAIR principles. To date, the only development methodology that explicitly incorporates FAIR principles is the LOT methodology [PFFG22], first introduced in 2022. Additionally, the FAIR in Practice Task Force has noted that the Humanities domain (in its broad sense) lacks repositories capable of managing complex digital objects, such as SAs [Eur20, 8]. This issue is also reflected in the evidence collected via H-SeTIS: HSAs are not supported by a shared repository infrastructure and are instead disseminated in various ad hoc ways, such as single RDF or Turtle files, or through static web pages. Only a few thesauri are hosted using dedicated semantic-thesaurus platforms, such as the Vocab Services managed by the Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage of the Austrian Academy of Sciences [SV24b, SV24e, SV24f]. Despite the large number of HSAs available on the web, their discovery and reuse are not straightforward. This is primarily due to the absence of standardized, detailed metadata capable of effectively describing ontologies and supporting their evaluation by users. The Metadata for Ontology Description and Publication (MOD) vocabulary was developed to address this gap, providing a dedicated metadata standard aimed at enhancing the discoverability and reusability of SAs [GBW24] (see Subsection 2.4).

Using FOOPS! (Ontology Pitfall Scanner for FAIR) [GCPV21], the authors evaluated the FAIRness of nine ontologies developed for, or of particular relevance to, the Heritage domain. These ontologies are among the few recorded in H-SeTIS that provide at least resolvable URIs, enabling their evaluation through FOOPS!.

The comparative analysis of the FAIRness of different typologies of HSA further reveals some interesting aspects. The group of ontologies examined (Figure 3) is quite comprehensive, ranging from cases like ArCo [SV24a] and FaBiO [SV24g] that score an overall high level of FAIRness, to cases like CIDOC CRM-Dig [SV24d] that reach a relatively low general level of FAIRness. A clear imbalance is visible even within the same ontology ecosystem, *i.e.* the CIDOC CRM and its extensions: for instance, while CIDOC [SV24c] and CIDOC-Erlangen [SV25c] are more prone to Accessibility, CRM-EH [SV25a] and CRM-Archaeo [SV25b] tend more towards Interoperability.

A different visualization of the same data (Figure 1) highlights the differences for each FAIR principle, with Accessibility and Interoperability that seems to have higher scores – Interoperability in particular, with six HSAs out of nine scoring equal or close to the highest values – while Findability and Reusability account for lower scores. Despite this general trend, some differences can be still found. For what concerns Findability, FaBiO scores 8.83/9: it has a persistent URL, its URIs are resolvable and correspond to the

Figure 1: Radar charts showing the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability of nine HSAs (ontologies; SA 1 = CIDOC; SA 2 = CIDOC Erlangen; SA 3 = CIDOC-CRM Dig; SA 4 = CRM-EH; SA 5 = CIDOC CRM Archaeo; SA 6 = ArCo; SA 7 = BIBO; SA 8 = FaBiO; SA 9 = lemon) assessed via FOOPS!.

ontology IDs, there are version IRIs that resolve to the different ontology versions, which also differ from the ontology main resolvable URI; it has minimum metadata (despite license data being missing); the ontology includes the declaration of its own prefix `fabio:`; the prefix declaration has a correct namespace, which is found in the LOV repository [VAPV17]. Conversely, CIDOC CRM-Dig, which has the lowest score among the analyzed ontologies (1/9), only has a resolvable URL. A similar trend can be identified also for the Interoperability principle: FaBiO scores 3/3 because the ontology is available in RDF, reuses existing vocabularies for embedded metadata and imports at least one other vocabulary.

CIDOC CRM-Dig scores 0/3 because it does not match any of the previous criteria.

For what concerns thesauri, the general overview appears to be more balanced (Figure 4). While few cases (RAMEAU [SV24], Tesoros del Patrimonio Cultural - Diccionario Geográfico [SV24]) seem to lack in Reusability, most of the other HSAs present much more similar results, especially for what concerns Accessibility and Interoperability, all with scores of 2/3 and 1/3 respectively. The more uneven FAIR principle for what concerns thesauri seems to be Reusability, with OeAI Thesaurus - Cultural Time Periods [SV24] which has the highest score, much higher than the average for thesauri.

Applying the FAIR principles to SAs enhances not only their findability and accessibility, but—most critically—their machine-actionability. This means that an SA must be structured in a way that allows computers to access, interpret, and utilize it without requiring human intervention. Such structuring enables the automation and acceleration of data discovery and reuse, achieving a level of efficiency and scalability that would be unattainable with purely human-actionable tools. As a result, ensuring the FAIRness of SAs is not just beneficial—it is a fundamental requirement for their effective integration into modern data ecosystems.

2.2. Use Semantic Versioning

Semantic versioning (SemVer) is a best practice in software development for systematically numbering software releases [Pre]. The "semantic" in semantic versioning has nothing to do with the Semantic Web and refers to the idea that each part of the version number conveys meaningful information about the software's evolution. Each release serves as a snapshot of the software at a specific stage in its development, as some updates may introduce improvements, new features, or changes—some of which could break compatibility with previous versions. When followed correctly, semantic versioning provides clear expectations about the stability of a release and helps users and developers determine whether an update will be safe or require adjustments. The version number in semantic versioning follows the format MAJOR.MINOR.PATCH (e.g., 2.3.4): MAJOR (2.x.x) defines a major version (changes that may not be backward compatible), MINOR (x.3.x) a minor version (new features are present, but backward compatibility is ensured), and PATCH (x.x.4), which includes bug fixes or minor improvements.

Although SemVer can technically be applied to any software, in the context of SA development, the adoption of certain best practices—whether language-agnostic or language-specific—ensures that SemVer communicates clear and consistent expectations for each release. Despite the lack of native support for SemVer in some standards (such as RDFS or SKOS), its application is still strongly recommended. Note that ontologies, and SAs in general, are to be intended as software [SWM04, sub §6].

Let us assume you are developing a SKOS thesaurus on typologies of vase shapes in Mesopotamia. As your thesaurus evolves, it will expand and improve over time. Enhancing its interoperability through mappings to other existing thesauri—such as the Art &

Architecture Thesaurus of the Getty Institute—may introduce compatibility improvements. You may also implement minor updates, such as correcting typographical errors or refining definitions. Although SKOS does not offer native versioning mechanisms and is itself language-agnostic, the W3C SKOS Core Guide [MB05] recommends the integration of versioning through the use of OWL properties (e.g., `owl:priorVersion`) and Dublin Core terms (e.g., `dcterms:hasVersion`, `dcterms:isReplacedBy`) integrated in a tailored concept scheme. The Web Ontology Language (OWL) [DSB*04] offers more robust tools for managing ontology versioning, such as `owl:versionIRI`, which allows developers to assign persistent identifiers to specific versions of a SA, and `owl:versionInfo`, which provides human-readable descriptions of changes (e.g., indicating the SemVer version) [GP20]. Implementing these mechanisms from the outset supports better transparency, traceability, and long-term sustainability of the thesaurus.

For example, CIDOC includes basic version data through the use of `owl:versionInfo` and provides more detailed information via `rdfs:comment`. However, a closer examination of CIDOC’s versioning reveals a more complex picture. In version 7.0.1, for instance, the model improves scope notes and first-order logic descriptions, yet the functionality remains unchanged from 7.0.0. In contrast, version 7.1.0 (a minor update) introduces more significant changes: the class `E98 Currency` is no longer a subclass of `E55 Type`, which is evident upon comparing the documentation of both versions. Removing a subclass relationship is considered a backward-incompatible change because it alters the ontology’s structure and can disrupt systems that rely on that relationship.

An overall evaluation of the changes made to CIDOC reveals that while it employs a structured versioning system, it does not strictly adhere to conventional SemVer principles. Each new version—whether in CIDOC or other software—represents a trade-off between additions and subtractions. As a result, a quantitative evaluation of changes (Figure 2) provides limited insight unless accompanied by a changelog. What might appear to be an improvement in one area could result in a regression in another. A deeper look at CIDOC’s major, minor, and patch versions uncovers unclear rules regarding the criteria for transitioning from patch to minor, or from minor to major versions.

As previously suggested [GP20, 4-5], SemVer should adhere to specific criteria, particularly to clearly indicate breaking changes and backward-compatible modifications. This approach ensures that the version number itself provides enough information to inform end users about the nature of changes (see Table 1).

Change Type	SemVer
New classes/properties representing new use cases	MAJOR
Deprecation/removal of elements	MAJOR
New single class/property that <i>extends</i> semantics	MINOR
Definition/scope note refinement	PATCH
Typos, grammar, bug fixes, minor updates	PATCH

Table 1: SemVer applied to SA versioning [GP20, 4-5].

Figure 2: Timeline of additions and deletions to the CIDOC XML file since the first version (4.0, issued in March 2004, not shown) to version 7.1.1, generated through mock Git versioning. The bars represent lines of code added (blue) and removed (red) in each commit, with version labels displayed along the timeline.

Since SAs are typically tailored to the needs of a specific community, they should address the community’s evolving requirements and expectations. Versioning offers the crucial advantage of enabling the community to clearly identify and track changes over time. However, understanding the nature of these changes requires more than just version numbers. Changelogs—records of all modifications made to a file or project—serve this purpose: they allow alterations to be systematically tracked and effectively communicate the nature, scope, and impact of each modification. When combined with SemVer, changelogs provide end users with a clear, up-to-date view of the SA’s status at any given time. Online code repositories such as GitHub and GitLab facilitate effective changelog

management while also supporting the versioning and release management of SAs. In addition, they offer substantial features to promote community engagement, such as issue tracking. This functionality—locally implemented by CIDOC, for instance (https://cidoc-crm.org/issue_summary)—enables developers to interact with the user community and allows users to better understand the rationale behind specific changes.

In the case of HSAs, tracking changes—although rarely implemented—is particularly important, as most choices often reflect compromises between diverse community needs and perspectives that may not be immediately apparent to the broader community. For instance, during the development of the ontology for the Heritage Science domain [SVR25], the authors' engagement with subject-matter experts revealed that even seemingly straightforward concepts, such as the definition of what an inscription is, prompted extensive debate and negotiation. Practices such as SemVer, changelog management, and issue tracking are therefore essential foundations for ensuring the long-term sustainability, transparency, and reusability of the model.

User documentation can be likened to an instruction manual, as it provides essential information on how a SA can be used, offers guidelines for its implementation, and supports use cases and applications. It is important to emphasize that project deliverables, while now commonly available as research outputs, do not replace user documentation. The latter must be regularly updated to remain relevant and functional to the SA reuse. CIDOC is one of the few HSAs that consistently implements and updates user documentation, while providing regular technical reports, serving as a model for best practices in the field.

The last documentation type—development documentation—builds upon the previous types by providing additional details on the processes behind the development of the SA. This includes information on contribution guidelines, update policies, and how the overall development process is managed. Unfortunately, very few HSAs provide insight into the modeling methodologies they adopt, nor is there clarity on how author contributions are tracked or how the community can engage with the developers.

The importance of providing different types of documentation for a SA, as highlighted above, should not overshadow the fact that users themselves must regularly and carefully consult the SA's documentation. As emphasized earlier, one of the core principles of semantic technologies and Linked Data is reusability. Providing insufficient documentation, or neglecting to consult the existing one, can equally and dangerously hinder the effective reuse and long-term sustainability of a SA.

2.3. Do not leave us hanging: Responsiveness expectations

The responsiveness status of a SA reflects its level of maintenance, its ability to meet its intended functions, and the engagement of its editors or working group. In the absence of a shared repository infrastructure, as well as the lack of SemVer, changelog management, and issue tracking for most HSAs, the task of assessing an HSA's responsiveness status often falls to the user. As part of the H-SeTIS survey, the authors introduced a classification system of five responsiveness statuses—adapted from the OBO Foundry

initiative [JMO*21]—to describe the current state of a SA, based, where possible, on direct communication with its authors. These statuses are:

- **Active:** The HSA has a contact person who is responsive. New terms, elements, or features are being added if the HSA is still evolving, or other revisions are made in response to community requests and/or the goals of the editorial team. IRIs are implemented and maintained if needed.
- **Inactive:** The HSA has a responsive contact person, and a current version is available. However, no updates or edits are being made, and requests for changes are either significantly delayed or are not being addressed by the editors.
- **Unresponsive:** The HSA does not have a responsive contact person, but it is still actively maintained. Although updates continue, there is no direct interaction with users or response to external requests.
- **Orphaned:** The HSA was designed and potentially developed to some extent, but it is no longer actively maintained, updated, or supported. The HSA lacks a responsive contact person, and no further edits or updates are being made. Inquiries or requests for edits are not addressed. The HSA is not deprecated or obsolete, but users should be aware that it is effectively discontinued.
- **Obsolete:** The HSA is no longer maintained (either inactive or orphaned), and its original developers do not recommend its use. This may be because a newer, more suitable resource is available, or previous versions have significant issues or are no longer accessible. Generally, "Obsolete" is a special status that should be assigned by the HSA's representative, which confirms that the HSA is formally deprecated. This practice is not widespread in the Heritage field.

2.4. Write the docs, read the docs

In the Heritage field, documentation for SAs has traditionally been published—if at all—through academic papers. Yet, good documentation is the foundation of effective use. When software—including ontologies and SAs at large, as they are intended to be [SWM04, sub §6]—is well documented, users can find answers to their questions and use it efficiently. Poor or absent documentation, on the other hand, hinders or even prevents reuse.

The Schema.org metadata standard, for instance, offers extensive documentation hosted on GitHub (<https://github.com/schemaorg/docsite>). Similarly, the OBO Relation Ontology (<https://oborel.github.io/>) documentation is built using MkDocs and hosted on GitHub Pages (<https://www.mkdocs.org/>). To support thorough ontology documentation, templates such as the Minimum Information for the Reporting of an Ontology (MIRO, <https://github.com/owlcs/miro>) guidelines [MMMS18] offer a framework for producing consistent and comprehensive documentation. While designed for ontologies, the MIRO guidelines can be effectively applied to other SAs, such as thesauri. All these solutions are easily implementable and require no development of additional tools, providing a straightforward and viable way to deliver basic or structured documentation. It is important to note, however, that documentation and scientific publications related to a SA are distinct outputs. While scientific publications serve as a means of introducing and describing the SA to

an academic community, they do not replace the documentation, which should delve into the technical aspects and provide the kind of detailed insight that a scientific paper typically cannot accommodate.

The OBO Foundry guidelines further recommend categorizing documentation into four types: *embedded*, *local*, *user*, and *development* documentation (see Principle 8 on documentation, <https://obofoundry.org/principles/fp-008-documented.html>). Embedded documentation corresponds to embedded metadata describing the SA and should be integrated within the artifact itself. Good practices for embedded metadata in ontologies have already been highlighted [GP20, 6-8], and more updated guidelines have recently been proposed in the framework of the FAIR-IMPACT project [GPF*23, GBW24].

The MOD (Metadata for Ontology Description and Publication Ontology) [DTEJ17, JTDE18, GBW24] is an ontology entirely devoted to describing SAs. It defines a detailed metadata standard for SA description. Notably, MOD and its documentation [DTEJ17, 173] [GBW24] often refer to knowledge artifacts and knowledge organization systems as ontologies, *i.e.*, SAs.

As an ontology itself, MOD offers a well-defined, comprehensive schema for describing SAs through a structured vocabulary of classes, object properties, and data properties. The schema is guided by principles such as brevity, clarity, interoperability, and standardization. Expressed in OWL, MOD aligns with major Semantic Web standards including Dublin Core, FOAF, and SKOS, ensuring high interoperability. MOD's development followed a combined top-down and bottom-up approach. The top-down method conceptualized broad aspects of ontology description, such as general information, authority, rights, and technical environment. The bottom-up approach drew on empirical data from user surveys. This dual perspective allows MOD to address both theoretical concerns and practical needs.

MOD represents a major step forward in the management of SAs, offering a standardized, interoperable, and user-informed vocabulary for ontology description. Its application can enhance the efficiency of ontology libraries and support broader Semantic Web goals—particularly through improved organization, discovery, and reuse of ontological resources. These benefits are especially relevant in the Heritage field, where the semantic landscape is highly fragmented, and artifacts vary widely in terms of development, responsiveness, and accessibility.

To the authors' knowledge, HSAs rarely provide detailed embedded documentation, which is pivotal to ensuring the FAIRness of an (H)SA. The role of embedded metadata in enhancing FAIRness has been extensively investigated within FAIR-IMPACT: minimum, recommended, and optional metadata elements have been proposed to support discoverability and reuse [GPF*23, 22-23]. It is therefore advisable to include embedded documentation in HSAs, and the MOD ontology offers a practical and ready-to-use solution for this purpose.

MOD divides embedded documentation into thirteen sections. The *General* section describes basic information, including the title (`dcterms:title`), acronym (`mod:acronym`), URI (`mod:URI`), and version informa-

tion (`owl:versionInfo`). Here, MOD reuses or redefines object and data properties from the Ontology Metadata Vocabulary [HPS*05], such as `mod:hasFormalityLevel` or `mod:hasRepresentationLanguage`, to indicate the level of formality (e.g., schema, taxonomy, terminology, thesaurus, vocabulary) or the language used to represent the SA (e.g., OWL). This is particularly relevant, as OWL 2 DL, for example, is more expressive than OWL. Additionally, several SAs may span multiple formality levels, making formality a nuanced and sometimes difficult parameter to define.

The *Licensing* section includes information on the type of license and access rights (e.g., `dcterms:license`). HSAs often fail to embed this kind of metadata or declare it informally in ways that are difficult to identify. Yet, licensing is a pivotal element for enabling reuse (FAIR principle R1.1). While many HSAs adopt a Creative Commons license, an undeclared or ambiguous license can still prevent effective reuse. Where possible, licenses should be referenced via a resolvable URI, such as <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>, to support interoperability.

The *Description* section provides information about the SA's scope and includes related bibliographic resources useful for contextual understanding. The *Dates* section specifies when the artifact was created (`dcterms:created`) and last modified (`dcterms:modified`). This information is particularly important for assessing the SA's responsiveness status (see also 2.3) and to determine whether the SA predates key developments such as the FAIR principles or Linked Data. Dates should follow the `xs:date` format (YYYY-MM-DD).

The *Persons and Organizations* section documents the authorship and curatorship of the SA, also crediting translators, publishers, and funding sources. Like the Dates section, these metadata support assessments of SA responsiveness by, for example, including a `dc:contactPoint`—an individual who can be contacted. As a general rule, creators (`dcterms:creator`), contributors (`dcterms:contributor`), or other involved parties should be referenced with both their full name and ORCID ID, providing a unique and persistent URI to prevent ambiguity.

The *Community* section includes metadata about how users can engage with the SA's community of authors and developers. This may involve specifying a code repository (`doap:repository`) and listing known bugs or issues (`doap:bugDatabase`). HSAs are rarely hosted in publicly accessible repositories, and community engagement is seldom encouraged. However, MOD emphasizes that SAs should address community needs—a goal that can only be achieved through active interaction with end users and subject-matter experts.

The *Documentation* section also provides guidance on how specific metadata elements contribute to the four FAIR principles and their sub-guidelines (e.g., via `prov:wasInfluencedBy`). For instance, `mod:usedInProject` links an SA to projects where it has been adopted, supporting FAIR principle I3: "(Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data." The *Usage* section focuses on the SA's usability, including information about the engineering methodology employed

(`mod:usedEngineeringMethodology`) and how new resources are added to the SA (`dcterms:accrualMethod`).

Object Description Properties are used to provide metadata for each individual element within the SA. For example, a property's label should be defined with `rdfs:label`, its description with `dcterms:description`, and its creation date with `dcterms:issued`. These metadata are essential for effective maintenance and for tracking improvements and additions to the SA over time. The *Links* section provides further correlations with other SAs, e.g. via `dctems:source`, which in MOD lists URIs of other SAs related to the one described and most importantly `dcat:downloadURL`, which provides the URLs where the described SA can be downloaded. The *Relations* section further includes relations of the SA with its own versions (`owl:priorVersion`). The information of `dcterms:relation` is particularly important as they list other SAs used/referred in the described one, providing information on reuse. This section also provides information on (in)compatibility of the SA with other SAs (`owl:backwardCompatibleWith`, `owl:incompatibleWith`). The *Content* section provides details on the scope and technical details of the SA, such as `vann:preferredNamespacePrefix` which defines the preferred namespace prefix to use when using terms from the described SA in an XML document. Direct reuses should be indicated with `mod:vocabularyUsed`. With the exception of metadata related to general information, licensing, and descriptions, other MOD metadata are seldom implemented in HSAs.

Local ontology documentation, which is embedded within the ontology itself, provides micro-management metadata for each component. For example, the Ontology for Biomedical Investigations [BBB*16] includes a set of properties dedicated to documenting changes, improvements, and modifications applied to every class, object property, or annotation property within ontologies belonging to the foundry. SKOS also offers basic tools for local documentation, such as `skos:editorialNote` and `skos:changeNote`. However, this kind of metadata should be kept separate from scope notes and descriptions to maintain machine-actionability; including it within these fields would hinder this functionality. To the authors' knowledge, local ontology documentation for HSAs is rarely implemented, which represents an opportunity for improvement in the field.

3. Conclusions

The <H/RADIOSA> initiative (see Table 2) and the OBO Foundry's work share the goal of promoting the integration of high-quality standards and SAs compliant standards within their respective domains. The H-SeTIS survey revealed a rich yet fragmented scenario, where most of the HSAs lack at least one of the four FAIR principles. No shared guidelines or best practices seem to be extensively applied to HSAs, resulting in a significant number of orphaned resources. This heterogeneity reduces the impact of semantic technologies for Heritage, as it directly impairs the effectiveness of the FAIR principles. Indeed, many HSAs were developed using methodologies that predate the FAIR principles and Linked (Open) Data, which explains their struggle to integrate these paradigms. Our evaluations, such as those performed using FOOPS!, clearly in-

dicate that Findability and Reusability are particularly challenging in the Heritage domain for HSAs, with generally lower scores compared to Accessibility and Interoperability. For instance, CIDOC CRM-Dig scored very low on Findability (1/9) due to a lack of resolvable URLs and on Interoperability (0/3) because it did not reuse existing vocabularies.

The inherently fragmented semantic landscape of the Heritage field and the project-focused (e.g., highly circumscribed) nature of many HSAs further limit their broad reuse and interoperability. A severe need affecting HSAs is this lack of shared, interoperable vocabularies, which strongly impairs both reusability and interoperability. While the OBO Foundry has a comprehensive set of principles to guide ontology development, an analysis by [XJG*23] to define quantifiable "FAIR Vocabulary Features" (FVFs) based on OBO principles found that not all OBO principles were directly suitable for this purpose, particularly those focusing on the developers or community rather than the semantic artefact as a digital object itself. In summary, 'H/RADIOSA' leverages the foundational work and lessons from the OBO Foundry, adapting its principles for the specific needs and challenges of the Heritage domain. It aims to provide a practical toolkit that organizes and highlights often-overlooked practices, such as consistent versioning with Semantic Versioning (SemVer) and changelogs, comprehensive documentation using frameworks like MIRO and MOD1, and clear licensing declarations. Ultimately, 'H/RADIOSA' seeks to bridge the gap between effective domain modeling and the minimum requirements for producing truly FAIR- and Linked Data-compliant semantic artefacts in the Heritage field.

Acknowledgements

H2IOSC Project - Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud funded by the European Union – NextGenerationEU – NRRP M4C2 - Project code IR0000029 - CUP B63C22000730005.

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Key Area	Specific Challenge	Key Tools and Areas for Improvement
FAIR Principles	HSAs often lack full FAIR compliance, due to methodologies predating FAIR and Linked Data. Many were developed using methodologies that predate FAIR principles.	FAIR principles now extend from research data to (H)SAs. FAIRsFAIR provides recommendations and practical solutions for FAIR principles integration. The FAIR-IMPACT project explicitly support converting legacy vocabularies to FAIR one. Assessment Tools like FOOPS!, F-UJI, and the O'FAIRe methodology automatically assess FAIRness.
Standardized Metadata	Severe lack of standardized, detailed metadata for HSAs, hindering discoverability and reusability.	MIRO Guidelines offer a framework for consistent and comprehensive ontology documentation. MOD Ontology was developed as an ontology specifically designed for describing semantic artefacts, enhance their discoverability and reusability. MOD reuses/aligns with Dublin Core, FOAF, and SKOS.
Semantic Versioning (SemVer) and Provenance	Tracking changes is rarely implemented in HSAs, despite being crucial due to community compromises and evolution of concepts. Provenance information is often missing.	The W3C SKOS Core Guide and OWL properties promote and support versioning. Version control systems like GitHub and GitLab facilitate traceable maintenance and changelog management for FAIR vocabularies. FAIRsFAIR P-Rec 17 stresses that provenance must be clear for both humans and machines. MIRO guidelines also list "provenance" and "lifecycle information" as MUST-report items. The MOD ontology includes versioning tools and links to projects.
Community-driven Development and Documentation	HSAs are often developed without shared guidelines, leading to orphaned resources and reduced impact due to inconsistencies. Definitions and design choices reflect compromises, which can be obscure to the broader community.	HSAs should be community-driven and address evolving needs. FAIRsFAIR BP.7 encourages user-centric development and interaction with designated communities. OBO Foundry Principle 6 (Textual Definitions) mandates textual definitions for classes and top-level terms. FAIRsFAIR BP.8 also recommends structured definitions for concepts. Good documentation is the foundation of effective use and prevents incorrect reuse.

Table 2: H/RADIOSA's first set of actions for enhancing HSA development and management.

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